

Statistics on seismic moment tensors for the Aegean Sea and surrounding area: preliminary results

Dasoula M. G.^{1*}, Roumelioti Z.¹, Sokos E.¹, Kokkalas, S.¹

(1) *Department of Geology, University of Patras, Patras, Greece, *up1074036@ac.upatras.gr*

Abstract

Moment tensors (MTs) are an essential tool for understanding earthquake source processes, improving seismic hazard assessment at various scales, and mitigating earthquake disaster risk. The Aegean Sea and its environs have the highest seismic activity in Europe and the Eastern Mediterranean, providing a wealth of earthquake data that can be used for moment tensor computations. In this work, we summarize moment tensor solutions published by the Global Centroid Moment Tensor Group (GCMT) and compare a subset of them with corresponding moment tensors from the Institute of Geodynamics of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). We statistically examine the two datasets, primarily from the point of view of the style of faulting implied by the moment tensors in the study area and the associated M_w reporting. We also analyze the metrics of this comparison with respect to various factors, such as the location and magnitude of the associated earthquakes, their hypocentral depth, etc. Overall, we find a good agreement between the moment tensors of GCMT and NOA for 85% of the cases studied. Poor comparisons are mostly restricted to moderate magnitude events along the Hellenic Arc.

Moment tensors of the Global Centroid Moment Tensor Group

There are many institutions and universities around the world that study seismic data and publish MTs. The reliability of each is an issue that often concerns researchers. When conducting seismic research on a particular area, the GCMT project MTs are often used as a reference, as they are the most widely accepted by the seismological community. For more than 40 years, the GCMT project has provided MTs for strong to moderate earthquakes around the globe using methods that involve inversion of long-period seismic waveforms based on normal mode summation and a 1D Earth model with path corrections (Dziewonski et al., 1981). In 2004, GCMT methods and processing underwent significant changes towards the incorporation of intermediate-period surface waves (Ekström et al., 2014). This led to improvements in shallow earthquake source parameters and a significant reduction in the smallest earthquake size for which GCMT publishes solutions.

In this first part of our work, we review all published GCMT solutions for the wider Aegean region (the exact study area is shown in Figure 1a), with statistics focusing on the implied style of faulting and moment magnitude, M_w , reporting. In total, we review 746 solutions, whose epicenters are shown in Figure 1a. The distribution of solutions unsurprisingly follows the distribution of seismicity in the area, with most MTs corresponding to earthquakes along the Hellenic arc, in the transition area of the Ionian islands, the Gulf of Corinth, and a zone subparallel to the western coast of Turkey. The well-known North Aegean trough zone collects a fair number of solutions, but is not as pronounced as in the seismicity maps. Figure 1b shows the distribution of solutions with M_w or M_w _GCMT to distinguish from another subset in the following. Nearly 80% of the dataset consists of solutions for earthquakes with $M_w < 5.5$. Figure 1c shows how the M_w in GCMT MTs is distributed over time and clearly reflects the methodological change of GCMT in 2004, which resulted in a sudden appearance of much smaller earthquakes in the catalog.

The MTs were classified according to the implied fault style following the projection technique of Kaverina et al. (1996) and the classification scheme of Álvarez-Gómez (2014, 2019) implemented in the FMC software. The scheme is based on the plunges of the three eigenvectors of the moment tensors (P, B, T axes) and their relations and includes seven types of faulting: normal (N), normal with strike-slip component (N-SS), strike-slip with normal component (SS-N), strike-slip (SS), strike-slip with reverse component (SS-R), reverse with strike-slip component (R-SS) and reverse (R). The projection of the classification diagram is shown in the inset of Figure 2a. Figure 2a shows the projections of all 746 MTs, with the dimensions of the circle symbols analogous to the size of the earthquakes and their color reflecting the hypocentral depth. About 43% of the MTs are classified as N or N-SS, 23% as R or R-SS, and 34% as SS, SS-N, or SS-R. Overall, almost half of the GCMT MTs for the study area are normal or have some normal faulting component. However, Figure 2b, which shows the cumulative seismic moment release per faulting class, clearly indicates that reverse faulting is the predominant type. This is also reflected in the concentration of larger earthquakes (larger circles in the lower right part of the plot in Figure 2a). Considering that more than 82% of the total seismic moment released by the 746 earthquakes in our dataset comes from the 55 M_w _GCMT ≥ 6.0 events, i.e., above the magnitude of completeness of the GCMT catalog for the Aegean area, at least since 1985 (González,

2024), the statistics in Figure 2b can be considered representative of the total seismic activity in the Aegean region for the examined time period.

Figure 1. a) Map of the study region showing the epicenters of earthquakes with reported moment tensors in the GCMT catalog and the distributions of b) solutions in M_w bins and c) M_w with time.

Another interesting observation in Figure 2a is the concentration of most intermediate depth earthquake MTs near the center and more generally in the mixed faulting parts of the diagram. This may reflect the increased complexity of the stress field and source processes at greater depths within the subducting system of the Aegean region, the uncertainty of data processing in such depths that result in mixed mode fault-type, the complexity of data from fault branching with decollement surfaces or any combination of these.

Figure 2. a) Faulting type classification diagram with seven types: N (normal), N-SS (normal with strike-slip component), SS-N (strike-slip with normal component), SS (strike-slip), SS-R (strike-slip with reverse component), R-SS (reverse with strike-slip component), R (reverse). Circle symbols are colored according to the hypocentral depth, and their dimensions are analogous to the magnitude of the earthquakes. The inset (after Álvarez-Gómez, 2014, 2019) shows the sectors of the diagram and corresponding classes b) pie chart with moment release by each class as a percentage of the total moment release from all earthquakes in the examined dataset.

Comparison of GCMT and National Observatory of Athens moment tensors: Faulting Style

The Institute of Geodynamics of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA) provides moment tensors for strong, moderate and even relatively weak earthquakes (down to $\sim M_w=3.5$) as part of its routine services. The MTs published so far by NOA, either automatically derived or manually processed, are based on full waveform inversion of regional broadband waveforms and can be divided into two parts. The first part includes the solutions for the period 2001-2011, when NOA used the method of Hermann and Ammon (2002) (e.g., Konstantinou et al., 2010; Konstantinou, 2015). The second part includes the MTs since 2012, derived by the method of Sokos and Zahradnik (2008), more recently extended by Zahradnik and Sokos (2018) and implemented in the software packages ISOLA and GISOLA (Triantafyllis et al., 2021). This is currently the method routinely used at NOA, and relevant results from its implementation are available on the institute's website (<https://bbnet.gein.noa.gr/HL/seismicity/mts>).

In order to quantify how well these regional MTs compare to those of the GCMT, we collected the seismic events that occurred in the Aegean and the wider area from 2001 to 2023, for which solutions are available from both sources (i.e., GCMT and NOA). We identified 450 events and as a result we created a database of 450 pairs of MTs. The locations of these events are shown on the map in Figure 3a.

We first examined the pairs of MTs for their similarity in implied fault geometry. To quantify similarity, we adopted an angular measure of the relative orientations of the two MTs in each pair, specifically the smallest angle required to rotate the principal axes of one MT into the principal axes of its paired MT. This angle has been studied extensively by Kagan (e.g., 1991, 2007) and is therefore often referred to as the "Kagan angle". A detailed description of the Kagan angle can be found in the aforementioned publications by Kagan himself and, for example, in Tape and Tape (2012) and references therein.

To define the Kagan angles for our dataset, we used the homonymous MATLAB function (Kolar, 2025). The results are incorporated into the map in Figure 3a by coloring the epicenters based on three classes of Kagan angles: $0^\circ - 30^\circ$, indicating that the two focal mechanisms are very similar, $30^\circ - 50^\circ$ for acceptable resemblance that allows the focal mechanisms to be identified as similar, and $>50^\circ$, where the two focal mechanisms in a pair are very different. Figure 3b shows examples of MT pairs from our dataset for different levels of Kagan angle. The distribution of computed Kagan angles in Figure 3a suggests that there is good agreement between GCMT and NOA solutions, i.e. most epicenters (85%) are colored blue (63%) or yellow (22%), implying Kagan angles $<50^\circ$. Red colored epicenters represent only 15% of the cases examined and are almost exclusively located in the outer parts of the study area, where earthquake epicenters are poorly covered in azimuth by the Hellenic Unified Seismological Network, the backbone data source for NOA MT inversions. The largest concentrations of high Kagan angles occur along the southeastern part of the Hellenic Arc and the Ionian Islands.

Figure 3. a) Map of the study region with epicenters of earthquakes for which both the GCMT and NOA have published MTs. Circle symbols are colored by Kagan angle ranges. b) Example pairs of MTs from the studied dataset for various levels of the Kagan angle.

Kagan angles were also examined as a function of earthquake magnitude (M_w), hypocenter depth, and time, as shown in Figure 4. Figure 4a shows the distribution of angles with the M_w _GCMT, where it is noticeable that high magnitude events (>6) have low Kagan angles. All angles $>50^\circ$ appear at lower magnitudes and especially at $M_w < 5.5$. Combining this observation with the distribution in Figure 3a leads to the expected result that MTs of events with $M_w < 5.5$ in the periphery of our study area are not always accurately resolved.

Figure 4b shows how the Kagan angles vary with the hypocentral depth of the events in our dataset. Most of the high Kagan angle values are concentrated at shallow depths, following the distribution of seismicity. However, several high angles appear to be distributed throughout the sampled depth interval, and the paucity of data at great depths does not allow us to draw any firm conclusions about a possible relationship between changes in the similarity of MT pairs and depth.

Finally, Figure 4c shows the Kagan angles with respect to the date of the events/MTs and gives the impression that the number of events associated with high angles has remained relatively stable over the years (2001-2023), despite the significant methodological changes by both GCMT and NOA. Moreover, since 2012, NOA has adopted GISOLA and has also allowed the release of automatic MT solutions, which has increased the number of events with MT pairs. The high Kagan angles have not followed this increase, indicating that the MT solutions provided by GCMT and NOA have become more similar in recent years.

Figure 4. Distribution of computed Kagan angles with respect to a) M_w _GCMT, b) the hypocentral depth of the earthquakes in the examined dataset and c) the date of occurrence of the earthquakes considered to coincide with the date of MT solutions release.

Comparison of GCMT and National Observatory of Athens moment tensors: M_w

The moment tensor is derived by modeling the full waveform and amplitude of the seismic waves, providing the most accurate measure of earthquake energy to date. The radiated seismic energy, in turn, is directly related to the seismic moment and, through it, to the M_w . Thus, the routine computation of MTs has provided a rich dataset of M_w values that should be consistent around the globe. However, it has been shown that different M_w catalogs can show systematic discrepancies. This is, for example, the case of M_w reported by GCMT and M_w reported by NOA based on their respective MT solutions as highlighted by Konstantinou (2015). Konstantinou (2015) collected MTs from GCMT and NOA concerning the same earthquakes and the period May 2001 to October 2014, formed a dataset of 185 paired MTs and examined the differences in their respective M_w values. He concluded that NOA M_w values are smaller than GCMT M_w values by 0.15-0.25 magnitude units and attributed this rather systematic difference to the limited bandwidth in NOA inversions methods with respect to GCMT.

In this final part of our work, we use our paired GCMT-NOA MTs to perform a similar comparison to that performed by Konstantinou (2014). It should be noted that in addition to the differences that may arise from the different methods, data, and metadata of the two MT solution sources, there are also minor differences that may result from the post-processing of the moment tensor metrics. These arise, for example, from the use of a slightly different relation to calculate M_w from the seismic moment, M_0 (Kanamori, 1977; Hanks and Kanamori, 1979), the form of these relations (i.e., to be used with M_0 in $N \times m$ or in $\text{dyn} \times \text{cm}$ and rounding tactics of the relations constants), and from different rounding tactics of the reported M_w . To constrain the latter, we have recalculated the M_w of both GCMT and NOA directly from the reported values of M_0 using Kanamori's (1979) relation. The comparison of the derived sets of M_w values is shown in Figure 5a and the result of the standard regression is expressed by the blue thick line described by:

$$M_w\text{-NOA} = 1.032(\pm 0.014)M_w\text{-GCMT} - 0.367(\pm 0.074) \quad (1)$$

Figure 5. a) Moment magnitude of NOA (M_w_{NOA}) versus moment magnitude of GCMT (M_w_{GCMT}) from the corresponding moment tensors. The thick blue line indicates the standard regression result of this study, the red line the orthogonal regression results of Konstantinou (2015) and the dashed gray line the 1:1 relation. b) Differences of the two examined M_w sets with the blue line marking the average difference of 0.2 magnitude units. c) Distribution of M_w differences in 0.15 difference bins.

Equation (1) shows a coefficient of determination $R^2=0.93$, which is slightly improved (by 0.01) compared to that of the relationship of Konstantinou (2015), despite the fact that our dataset is more than twice as large. Our result is also compared graphically with that of Konstantinou (2015) in Figure 5a, where it is evident that the two lines are practically identical in the upper half and differ only slightly towards lower magnitudes. In fact, our result seems to deviate more from the 1:1 line (gray dashed line) as the magnitude decreases.

Figures 5b,c show the distribution of the differences between the two magnitudes in our dataset, and the blue line shows the practically constant mean of -0.20. Almost all differences are below zero, confirming that M_w_{NOA} is systematically lower than M_w_{GCMT} .

Conclusions/Discussion

We present preliminary results of an extensive statistical investigation and comparison of moment tensors (MTs) of earthquakes in the Aegean Sea and surrounding area, using data from the Global Centroid Moment Tensor (GCMT) project and the Institute of Geodynamics of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). We investigate the MTs with respect to the implied faulting type during strong to moderate magnitude earthquakes in the area, the moment magnitudes (M_w), and the consistency between the two datasets.

Statistical analysis of the GCMT's 40-year archive of 746 MTs for the area showed that approximately 80% of this dataset consists of solutions for earthquakes with $M_w < 5.5$. It also showed that although normal faulting is more frequent, reverse faulting accounts for the largest share of seismic moment release in the form of larger earthquakes. This is consistent with the mechanics involved, which are not facilitated by gravity as in normal faulting, with compressional forces often "locking" large areas and preventing movement for extended periods. This allows for the long build-up of stress that is eventually released in larger magnitude earthquakes.

We also examined the comparison of 450 pairs of MTs from GCMT and NOA for earthquakes from 2001 to 2023. To quantify the similarity/difference in the proposed fault geometry, we used the Kagan angle and concluded that the two compared sets of MTs show good agreement in 85% of the cases studied. Poor comparison of MTs provided by GCMT and NOA for the same events was found for only 15% of the pairs studied and was mostly associated with moderate magnitude events ($M_w < 5.5$) along the Hellenic arc. Over time, despite methodological changes in both GCMT and NOA, the number of events with high Kagan angles has remained stable and the similarity between MT solutions may have increased over time, as suggested by the larger number of good comparisons in recent years.

A comparison of M_w values from GCMT and NOA MTs confirmed previous studies (e.g., Konstantinou, 2015) that NOA M_w values are systematically lower than GCMT M_w values by an average of 0.20 magnitude units. Regression analysis of M_w values showed that this difference is consistent across the magnitude range, with a slightly larger deviation from the 1:1 $M_w_{NOA} - M_w_{GCMT}$ relationship as magnitude decreases.

Acknowledgements

We acknowledge the Global Centroid Moment Tensor project and the National Observatory of Athens for the invaluable moment tensor data provided for decades. The study was carried out in the framework of the research project "UNMASK", supported by the

Hellenic Foundation for Research and Innovation (H.F.R.I.) under the “2nd Call for H.F.R.I. Research Projects to support Faculty Members & Researchers” (Project Number: 2724).

References

- Álvarez-Gómez, J. A., 2019. FMC—Earthquake focal mechanisms data management, cluster and classification. *SoftwareX*, 9, 299-307.
- Álvarez-Gómez, J. A., 2014. FMC: a one-liner Python program to manage, classify and plot focal mechanisms. *Geophysical Research Abstracts*, Vol. 16, EGU2014-10887
- Dziewonski, A. M., T.-A. Chou, J. H. Woodhouse, 1981. Determination of earthquake source parameters from waveform data for studies of global and regional seismicity. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 86, 2825-2852, doi:10.1029/JB086iB04p02825
- Ekström, G., M. Nettles, A.M. Dziewonski, 2012. The global CMT project 2004-2010: Centroid-moment tensors for 13,017 earthquakes, *Phys. Earth Planet. Inter.*, 200-201, 1-9, doi:10.1016/j.pepi.2012.04.002
- González, Á., 2024. Improvements and heterogeneities of the Global Centroid Moment Tensor catalog. *Seism. Res. Lett.* 95(6), 3566-3578.
- Hanks, T.C., H. Kanamori, 1979. A moment magnitude scale, *J. Geophys. Res.* 84(B5), 2348-2350.
- Herrmann, R.B., C.J. Ammon, 2002. Computer programs in seismology source inversions: User's manual, version 3.30, report, St. Louis University, St. Louis, Missouri.
- Kagan, Y. Y., 1991. 3-D rotation of double-couple earthquake sources, *Geophys. J. Int.*, 106(3), 709-716.
- Kagan, Y.Y., 2007. Simplified algorithms for calculating double-couple rotation. *Geophys. J. Int.* 171, 411–418.
- Kanamori, H., 1977. The energy release in great earthquakes. *J. Geophys. Res.* 82(20), 2981-2987.
- Kaverina, A.N., A.V. Lander, A.G. Prozorov, 1996. Global creep distribution and its relation to earthquake-source geometry and tectonic origin. *Geophysical Journal International* 125, 249–265.
- Kolar, P., 2025. Kagan angle (<https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/70040-kagan-angle>), MATLAB Central File Exchange. Retrieved January 24, 2025.
- Konstantinou, K.I., 2015. Moment Magnitude Estimates for Earthquakes in the Greek Region: A Comprehensive Comparison. *Bulletin of the Seismological Society of America* 105(5), 2555–2562, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120150088>
- Konstantinou, K.I., N.S. Melis, K. Boukouras, 2010. Routine Regional Moment Tensor Inversion for Earthquakes in the Greek Region: The National Observatory of Athens (NOA) Database (2001–2006). *Seismological Research Letters* 81(5), 750–760, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1785/gssrl.81.5.750>
- Sokos, E. N., J. Zahradník, 2008. ISOLA a Fortran code and a Matlab GUI to perform multiple-point source inversion of seismic data. *Computers and Geosciences*, 34, 967-977.
- Tape, W., C. Tape, 2012. Angle between principal axis triples. *Geophys. J. Int.*, 191, 813-831.
- Triantafyllis, N., I.E. Venetis, I. Fountoulakis, E.-V. Pikoulis, E. Sokos, Ch.P. Evangelidis, 2021. Gisola: A High-Performance Computing Application for Real-Time Moment Tensor Inversion. *Seismological Research Letters*, 93(2A), 957–966, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220210153>
- Zahradník, J., E. Sokos, 2018. ISOLA code for multiple-point source modeling, in: S. D'Amico (ed.), *Moment Tensor Solutions*, Springer Natural Hazards, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-77359-9_1